

ANALYSIS OF ENCRYPTION ALGORITHMS FOR CLOUD SECURITY

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Abstract. *Cloud computing is the next big thing after internet in the field of Information technology. It is an Internet-based computing technology, in which software, Shared recourses and information are provided to consumers and devices on-demand, and as per user's requirement on a pay per use model. Even though the cloud continues to grow in popularity, Usability and respectability, Problems with data protection and data privacy and other Security issues play a major setback in the field of Cloud Computing. Privacy and security are the key issue for cloud storage. Encryption is a well known technology for protecting sensitive data. This paper proposes a combined approach of Identity based and attribute based access policy for encryption technique of cloud storage which can be implementable on cloud platform. The report analyses the feasibility of the applying encryption algorithm for data security and privacy in cloud Storage with other existing algorithms.*

Keywords: *Cloud computing, Cryptography, Encryption, Decryption, Cipher Text, DES, TDES, AES, RSA, Homomorphic, IDEA, Blowfish.*

Introduction

Cloud computing is the fastest growing technology, offers various services over the internet. It can serve many facilities to the business such as resources, infrastructure, platform etc by paying amount on demand basis over network with the functionality of increase or decrease the requirements. This technology can meet any IT requirements at any time. It can serves most of the hardware and software facilities required for companies for storing, creating, managing, running consumer applications on cloud in lease or rent basis, it provides resources as a service to multiple consumers by virtualization. This technology helps many IT organizations to start up business without huge economical barriers, slowly move to leading organization in the industry. It can serve facilities irrespective of the size of organizations. These services gave new face to the computing technology. According to NIST, Cloud computing is a model for enabling convenient, ondemand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction [1]. Various cloud service providers are Amazon, Google, IBM, Microsoft, and Salesforce.com, offer their cloud infrastructure for services.

Security becomes big issue when any one stores its important information to a platform which is not directly controlled by the user and which is far away [1]. While

sending of data and during storage data is under threat because any unauthorised user can access it, modify it, so there is need to secure data. A data is secure, if it fulfils three conditions (i) Confidentiality (ii) Integrity (iii) Availability. Confidentiality means the data is understandable to the receiver only for all others it would be waste; it helps in preventing the unauthorised disclosure of sensitive information. Integrity means data received by receiver should be in the same form, the sender sends it; integrity helps in preventing modification from unauthorised user. Availability refers to assurance that user has access to information anytime and to any network. In the cloud confidentiality is obtained by cryptography. Cryptography is a technique of converting data into unreadable form during storage and transmission that it appears waste to intruder. The unreadable form of data is known as cipher text. When data is received by receiver it, will appear in its original form which is known as plain text. Conversion of plain text to cipher text is known as encryption and reverse of this (cipher text to plain) is known as decryption. Encryption takes place at sender's end whereas decryption takes place at receiver's end.

Figure 1. Encryption Decryption Process

Famous Cipher Algorithms

Users of cloud computing systems, whether they are physical or legal persons, store their data in the cloud, so protecting data from attackers is an important task.

Many algorithms are used to ensure the security of cloud computing. Below are some popular algorithms:

Data Encryption Standard (DES)

DES is very commonly used symmetric key algorithm. It was developed by IBM in 1974, but now a days many methods are found that had proven this algorithm unsecured [2].

In DES algorithms block cipher is of 64 bits [2] and key used is of 56 bits out of 64 bits of key is used rest of 8 bits are padded. In block cipher we encrypt block of data which consist of plain text by combination of confusion and diffusion to make cipher block then this cipher block has to pass 16 rounds, before passing through these 16 rounds the 64 bits of data is divided into 32 bits. After dividing the data into 32 bits, F-function (Feistel function) is applied. F-function consists of substitution, permutation, key mixing. The output of function is combined with other half of the data using XOR gate alternate crossing of data is done; then crossing of data is done.

Figure 2 - Diagram of DES Encryption Algorithm

After doing 16 such rounds cipher text is produced or encryption of data is done. To decrypt the data reverse operation is done. The drawback of DES is that key used in DES is very small and its security can be broken easily and DES works fast on hardware only and works slowly on software. As shown in Fig 3 data bits are divided into two parts L_f and R_f than F function and XOR operation is applied on R_f , and output is combined with L_f

Figure 3. Inside Working of DES Algorithm

Advance Encryption Standard (AES)

AES is a symmetric-key block cipher published by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). Most adopted symmetric encryption is AES. It operates computation on bytes rather than bits, treats 128 bits of plaintext block as 16 bytes. These 16 bytes are arranged in four columns and four rows for processing as a matrix. It operates on entire data block by using substitutions and permutations. The key size used for an AES cipher specifies the number of transformation rounds used in the encryption process. Possible keys and number of rounds are as following:

- 10 rounds for 128-bit keys.
- 12 rounds for 192-bit keys.
- 14 rounds for 256-bit keys.

Major advantages of AES over DES are:

- Data block size is 128 bits.
- Key size 128/192/256 bits depending on version.
- Most CPUs now include hardware AES support making it very fast.
- It uses substitution and permutations.
- Possible keys are 2128 , 2192 and 2256
- More secure than DES.
- Most adopted symmetric encryption algorithm.

Figure 4. Encryption with AES Algorithm

Triple- DES (TDES)

TDES is enhanced version of DES in TDES the key size is increased to increase i.e. 168 bits the security of data. In TDES only size of key is increased rest of the working is similar to DES. In TDES three different keys are applied on cipher block [3].

Figure 5. TDES Encryption Algorithm

Rivest-Shamir-Adleman (RSA)

RSA is a public key cipher developed by Ron Rivest, Adi Shamir and Len Adlemen in 1977. It is most popular asymmetric key cryptographic algorithm. This algorithm uses various data block size and various size keys. It has asymmetric keys for both encryption and decryption. It uses two prime numbers to generate the public and private keys. These two different keys are used for encryption and decryption purpose [3]. This algorithm can be broadly classified in to three stages; key generation by using two prime numbers, encryption and decryption. RSA today is used in hundreds of software products and can be used for key exchange, digital signatures, or encryption of small blocks of data. This algorithm is mainly used for secure communication and authentication upon an open communication channel.

While comparing the performance of RSA algorithm with DES and DES, When we use small values of p & q (prime numbers) are selected for the designing of key, then the encryption process becomes too weak and one can be able to decrypt the data by using random probability theory and side channel attacks. On the other hand if large p & q lengths are selected then it consumes more time and the performance gets degraded in comparison with DES. Operation speed of RSA Encryption algorithms is slow compare to symmetric algorithms, moreover it is not secure than DES.

Homomorphic Algorithm

It is an encryption algorithm that provide remarkable computation facility over encrypted data (cipher text) and return encrypted result. This algorithm can solve many issues related to security and confidentiality issues. In this algorithm encryption and

decryption taking place in client site and provider site operates upon encrypted data. This can solve threat while transferring data between client and service provider, it hide plaintext from service provider, provider operates upon ciphertext only. Homomorphic encryption allows complex mathematical operations to be performed on encrypted data without using the original data. For plaintexts X_1 and X_2 and corresponding ciphertext Y_1 and Y_2 , a Homomorphic encryption scheme permits the computation of $X_1 \oplus X_2$ from Y_1 and Y_2 without using $P_1 \oplus P_2$. The cryptosystem is multiplicative or additive Homomorphic depending upon the operation \oplus which can be multiplication or addition.

Results analysis

It was mentioned in that AES is faster and more efficient symmetric algorithms. When the transmission of data is considered there is insignificant difference in performance of different symmetric key schemes. This provide high security over open network but key transfer is the major issue in symmetric algorithms. Based on the text files used and the experimental result it was concluded[4] that DES algorithm consumes least encryption time and AES algorithm has least memory usage while encryption time difference is very minor in case of AES algorithm and DES algorithm, but RSA Encryption algorithms consume a significant amount of computing resources such as CPU time, memory, and battery power.

Comparison of secret key and public key based DES and RSA algorithms, it clears that RSA solves the problem of the key agreement and key exchange problem generated in secret key cryptography. But it does not solve all the security infrastructure So DES is used. RSA and DES differ from each other in certain features.

Paper specifies that RSA have many flaws in its design therefore not preferred for the commercial use. When the small values of p & q are selected for the designing of key then the encryption process becomes too weak and one can be able to decrypt the data by using random probability theory and side channel attacks. On the other hand if large p & q lengths are selected then it consumes more time and the performance gets degraded in comparison with DES.

According to research done and literature survey it can be found that AES algorithm is most efficient in terms of speed, time, throughput and avalanche effect. The Security provided by these algorithms can be enhanced further, if more than one algorithm is applied to data.

Based on the text files used and the experimental result it was concluded that AES algorithm consumes least encryption and RSA consume longest encryption time. We also observed that

Decryption of AES algorithm is better than other algorithms. From the simulation result, we evaluated that AES algorithm is much better than DES and RSA

algorithm [5]. It was concluded that Homomorphic cryptosystems allow for the same level of privacy as any other cryptosystem, while also allowing for operations to be performed on the data without the need to see the actual data. Complete privacy between client and server would be possible without any decreased functionality. Such systems could be applied to nearly anything that requires computation, such as voting, banking, cloud computing, and many others. It is concluded [6] that Homomorphic encryption is a new concept of security which enables providing results of calculations on encrypted data without knowing the raw data on which the calculation was carried out, with respect of the data confidentiality. Security of cloud computing based on fully Homomorphic encryption is a new concept of security which is able to provide the results of calculations on encrypted data without knowing the raw entries on which the calculation was carried out respecting the confidentiality of data.

Conclusion

Cloud computing is a new generation technology in the world of information technology. It has numerous advantages but some challenges still exist in this technology. Security is the most challenging issue in this technology. In this paper we have discussed various encryption algorithms to overcome this security issue, deals with advantages and disadvantages of these algorithms. Here we conclude that homomorphic algorithm is the most suitable algorithm in cloud computing environment to secure their valuable data in an open network. The ability of homomorphic algorithm to perform operations on encrypted data enables higher security than others algorithms such as RSA, DES, AES. Future work is to implement hardware or software techniques with homomorphic algorithm to provide protection on cloud from any type of security attack.

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